

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GUERRA****FIRST NAME: HEITOR****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Writing academic papers requires deliberate, thorough and careful thought. Therefore, what should one do to achieve a well-crafted academic essay?**

- One must depend on his/her own opinions alone.
- One must conduct research on the topic at hand.¹**
- One must not consult the Internet for unsure sources.
- One must depend highly on the Internet for easy information access.

¹ Griffith, Kelley, *Writing Essays about Literature: A Guide and Style Sheet* (Boston: Wadsworth Cengage Learning, 2014), 5-25.

2. **Which of the following results may arise when one successfully underwent the process of academic writing?**

- The questions posed by the writer will be answered.
- The problem raised by the writer will be clarified.
- The writer can argue for an opinion or stand.
- All the above.**²

3. **What is a claim?**

- a statement used to support or prove the thesis.**³
- quotations from a source.
- the analysis explaining the meaning of evidence.
- a sentence that grabs your reader's attention.

4. **Qualitative research is used in all the following circumstances, EXCEPT:**

- It is based on a collection of non-numerical data such as words and pictures.
- It often uses small samples.

² Turabian, Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 39-40.

³ Ibid., 58.

- It uses the inductive method.
- It is typically used when a great deal is already known about the topic of interest.**⁴

5. **Which is not a type of research design?**

- Nominal.**⁵
- Descriptive
- Exploratory
- Experimental

6. **What are research designs?**

- answer choices.
- The overall structure of your research.**⁶
- Using multi-methods to collect data.
- A way of measuring validity of your data collected.

7. **Which of the following best defines a hypothesis**

- An explanation of a topic.

⁴ Ibid., 87.

⁵ Creswell, John and Creswell David. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2018), 7-20.

⁶ Ibid., 45-60.

- A set of rules of conduct to be followed in research.
- A problem or statement to be investigated through research.**⁷
- A process used to select individuals to participate in research.

8. Define 'primary' data

- answer choices.
- Data collected from the internet.
- Data collected using other forms of media.
- Data collected through questionnaires, interviews, and observations.**⁸

9. Identify the classifications of data...

- Primary, secondary, discrete, Interviews, observations, and nominal.
- Discrete, secondary, interval, ratio and secondary.
- Secondary, discrete, ratio, interval, focus groups and observations.
- Nominal, ordinal, discrete, interval, ratio and continuous.**⁹

10. What is a thesis statement?

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 24-50.

⁸ Ibid., 36.

⁹ Ibid., 36-50.

- Is the sentence that tells the main idea of the whole essay.**¹⁰
- It the paragraph that presents the problems.
- Is the sentence that calls for action.
- spark interest to your audience.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Griffith, Kelley. *Writing Essays about Literature: A Guide and Style Sheet*. 9th ed. Boston: Wadsworth Cengage Learning, 2014

World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual*. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 1993.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

¹⁰ Ibid., 32-33.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.